

HEAT EXCHANGER NETWORK DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION FOR WATERBORN SOLID OXIDE FUEL CELL COGENERATION SYSTEM

Eduardo A. Pina^{1,2*}, Shivom Sharma^{1,2}, Amogh Amladi³, Theo Woudstra³, Purushothaman V. Aravind³, François Maréchal¹, Jan Van Herle²

¹École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Industrial Process and Energy Systems Engineering, 1950 Sion, Switzerland

²École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Group of Energy Materials, 1950 Sion, Switzerland

³ University of Groningen, Energy Conversion, Energy and Sustainability Research Institute, 9747 AG Groningen, The Netherlands

*Corresponding Author: eduardo.pina@epfl.ch

ABSTRACT

This study examines an integrated Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) cogeneration system fuelled by Liquefied Natural Gas for a cruise ship. The SOFC system comprises stack and balance of plant component, including pre-reformer, afterburner, heat exchangers (HEs), valves, and blowers. In addition to generating electricity for propulsion and other uses, waste heat is utilized to produce saturated steam (180 °C) and hot water (90 °C). Technical feasibility assessments are conducted for various conditions, focusing particularly on the practical implementation of the heat exchanger network (HEN) design to meet system heat demand and recover additional waste heat. The HEN should remain consistent for system operation at both Beginning-of-Life (BoL) and End-of-Life (EoL) conditions of the SOFC. Firstly, an SOFC model is developed in Aspen Plus, followed by multi-objective optimization to optimize system operating conditions considering net electrical efficiency, external water intake, and external air flow as objective functions. A suitable solution is chosen from the Pareto curve to conduct the HEN synthesis. A mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model was developed for the HEN synthesis, minimizing the number of HEs and achieving optimal matches between hot and cold streams. The MILP model makes crucial practical considerations, including forbidden stream matches due to safety constraints, pressure drops across HEs, and creating hot box to minimize heat losses. The HEs are sized using the logarithmic mean temperature difference method. The SOFC system has a nominal power capacity of about 125 kW. The trade-off solution presents net electric efficiencies of 60.3% (BoL) and 50.2% (EoL), with overall efficiencies of 77.5% (BoL) and 75.0% (EoL). For EoL conditions, the estimated HE area is 124.54 m², and high-grade waste heat is available for end-of-pipe utilization, producing approximately 1788.3 kg/day of steam and 1467.1 kg/day of hot water. The study demonstrates that the proposed HEN is suitable for both BoL and EoL conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The shipping industry is responsible for around 2.9% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions (IMO, 2020). At the European Union (EU) level, maritime transport represents 3–4% of the EU's total CO₂ emissions (Flodén et al., 2024). Presently, the world faces an important dichotomy related to climate regulations and emissions, a challenge that also involves the maritime industry. On the one side, the International Maritime Organization has established ambitious targets to reach net-zero emissions by 2050; simultaneously, the sector continued to rebound in 2022 following the drop during the covid-19 pandemics. Projections show that, by 2050, the sector's emissions could increase by up to 130% of 2008 levels (EC, 2024). This context emphasizes the urgency in proposing decarbonisation measures that transcend into practical actions, such as improvement in energy efficiency and innovative energy conversion technologies, as highlighted by the EU Directive 2018/410 (EC, 2018).

The use of fuel cells has attracted the growing attention of researchers and industries over the last decades, owing to their high efficiency and lower pollutant emissions, as a potential decarbonisation solution for the shipping industry (Elkafas et al., 2023). The Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) technology, in particular, has a marked advantage over other fuel cell technologies, offering higher fuel flexibility (e.g. methane, methanol, ammonia, diesel), higher electrical efficiency of around 60%, and higher-grade waste heat with overall efficiencies up to 85–90% (Baldi et al., 2020).

Operating at temperatures typically ranging from 800 to 1000 °C, SOFCs offer the advantage of cogenerating high-grade waste heat, making them ideal for Combined Heat and Power (CHP) applications. However, these very high temperatures also pose significant thermal management challenges. Effective dissipation of heat generated within the stack is key to minimize thermal stress, which can potentially lead to cell degradation and failure. Furthermore, SOFC performance is deeply linked to a combination of operating parameters, such as pressures, temperatures, and mass and energy flow rates, as well as system configurations (Xu et al., 2021). Therefore, proper thermal management is essential to maintain system performance, stability, reliability and longevity (Li et al., 2024).

The Heat Exchanger Network (HEN) synthesis aims to determine the best possible connections among hot and cold streams, creating a feasible system that optimizes waste heat recovery (Yee and Grossmann, 1990). Thus, properly designed HENs ensure a high level of waste heat recovery and minimum energy consumption of the system. Synthesizing the HEN constitutes a combinatorial problem with many possible matches that is typically solved by two main approaches: heuristic methods, i.e., the Pinch method, and mathematical programming techniques, such as Mixed-Integer (Non) Linear Programming (MILP/MINLP) (Ian C. Kemp, 2007).

There are several aspects that must be taken into account in the HEN design. One such aspect involves considering technical and practical limitations, including forbidden, restricted, and required matches. Additionally, it is necessary to address the flexibility of the HEN and its adaptation to diverse operating conditions, such as multi-product operation and part-load operation, which are characterized by different mass flow rates and temperatures of the streams during the different operating periods. Previous studies have addressed these aspects. Mian et al. (2016) proposed a framework for the multiperiod synthesis of HEN with optimal utility selection and scheduling. Wei et al. (2023) designed a shared HEN for a Reversible Solid Oxide Cell system, ensuring that both systems are highly integrated given the two different operation modes (fuel cell/electrolizer). Tanozzi et al. (2019) investigated the design of a HEN for a SOFC and gas turbine system for a hybrid vehicle, with a particular focus on the design of the HEs and the 3D space optimization. Nevertheless, the aforementioned flexibility must also extend throughout the lifecycle of the SOFC system, encompassing both Beginning-of-Life (BoL) and End-of-Life (EoL) conditions. This is the focus of the present study.

The aim of this study is to design a HEN for a 125 kW SOFC cogeneration system that produces saturated steam (180 °C) and hot water (90 °C) operating under BoL and EoL conditions. The main contribution is the focus on practical considerations for the HEN. The study is divided into four main steps: Firstly, the process model of the SOFC cogeneration system was developed to determine the mass and energy flow rates at nominal operation for both BoL and EoL conditions of the SOFC. Then, a multi-objective optimisation (MOO) procedure was applied to determine the optimal process operating conditions for maximum net electrical efficiency, minimum external water intake, and minimum external air flow. Secondly, the HEN was synthesized for the proposed trade-off solution. The optimal connections between hot and cold streams were identified, providing the base for sizing the HEs. Lastly, the availability of flue gas for producing saturated steam and hot water to meet the ship's thermal requirements was carried out.

2 SYSTEM MODELLING AND OPTIMISATION

2.1 System definition

The process model of the SOFC system was developed in Aspen Plus v11. The model of the SOFC stack employed thermochemical process units available in Aspen Plus and a Fortran-based calculator block to carry out the electrochemical calculations. All reactions in the SOFC were assumed to be isothermal and operating at the outlet temperature of the stack. The air and fuel inputs to the stack are given at 100 °C lower than the outlet temperature. The area-specific resistance (ASR) of the stack was

assumed to depend on temperature. The parameters used in the calculation were determined experimentally. The reduction in performance by EoL was modelled as an increase in the ASR with a constant factor, which was calculated such that the EoL power density was 0.2925 W/cm^2 .

The simplified process flow diagram of the SOFC system with balance-of-plant is shown in Figure 1. Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) from the tank is pumped through the system to overcome pressure losses. Water used for steam reforming is also pumped and then preheated and evaporated. The vaporized LNG and water are mixed with recirculated anode off-gas (AOG) and fed to the external pre-reformer after appropriate pre-heating. The water flow rate is modulated to ensure an oxygen:carbon atom ratio of 2. The reformer is an equilibrium reactor (a predefined temperature profile is not maintained through intentional heating/cooling, but a certain heat loss through the boundary could be assumed), and the extent of reaction is controlled via the inlet temperature with the preheater. After partial reforming, the LNG is then preheated and sent to the SOFC anode. The air used for oxidation and stack cooling is run through a blower, preheated, and then mixed with recirculated cathode off-gas (COG). The preheating temperature is controlled such that the desired cathode inlet temperature is reached upon mixing with recirculated COG.

Figure 1: Simplified process flow diagram of the SOFC system.

It was decided to use hot blowers (i.e. blowers that can withstand gases at the high stack outlet temperature), despite their low Technology Readiness Level and efficiency. This is to avoid large HEs to cool the AOG and COG, since this is meant for a mobile application. To represent assumed heat losses through the hot blower (either from the insulation, or cooling for the blades and motors), a 35 K temperature drop was implemented in a dummy cooler as part of the combustor. The AOG and COG, after the appropriate recirculation, are mixed and then sent to the afterburner to combust any remaining fuel molecules. A supplementary air stream was provided, though found to be rarely necessary, to limit the combustion temperature to $950 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The hot flue gas after combustion was first used as the heating source to provide process heat for the various heaters in the system, and subsequently, to produce saturated steam and hot water for the ship's needs in the end-of-pipe utilization.

The pressure drop in the system, in addition to the variable stack pressure drop, was assumed to be 80 mbar, with 40 mbar applied to the air and fuel preheaters, and 40 mbar applied to the flue gas cooler. The polytropic efficiency was assumed to be around 45% for the hot blowers, and 75% for the other blowers. The liquid pumps were assigned an isentropic efficiency of 85%. A mechanical efficiency of 95% was assumed for all blowers and pumps.

The electrical efficiency η_{el} is defined as per Eq. (1), where P_{SOFC} [W] is the gross power output of the SOFC, P_{aux} [W] is the auxiliary power consumed by blowers and pumps, \dot{m}_{LNG} [mol/s] is the molar flow rate of LNG, and LHV_{LNG} [J/mol] is the Lower Heating Value (LHV) of LNG. A typical LNG composition was taken from the International Maritime Organization (IMO), with 94% methane, 4.7%

ethane, 0.8% propane, 0.2% butane and 0.3% nitrogen, having a LHV of 843.42 kJ/mol. The fuel mixture's LHV may change during the reforming depending on the operating conditions, that is, the LHV would first reduce due to dilution with steam/AOG and then increase due to endothermic reforming. While this might impact the SOFC stack efficiency, for most system applications the net system efficiency is a much more relevant metric. The global fuel utilization was defined as the ratio of oxygen molecules consumed in the SOFC, represented by the current, to the oxygen molecules needed to oxidise all the LNG. The extent of pre-reforming was defined as the ratio of the number of carbon atoms converted from hydrocarbons to CO and CO₂ within the reformer, to the number of carbon atoms in hydrocarbons entering the reformer.

$$\eta_{el} = \frac{P_{SOFC} - P_{aux}}{\dot{m}_{LNG} \cdot LHV_{LNG}} \quad (1)$$

2.2 Multi-objective optimization

The starting point of the HEN design was the optimization of the SOFC system's performance under EoL conditions, which are characterized by a reduction in electrical efficiency due to performance degradation over the system's lifetime, coupled with an increase in waste heat generation and larger mass flow rates. Thus, the HEN must be designed for system operation under EoL conditions, and a verification must be made to ensure that the HEN configuration remains consistent for system operation under BoL.

Figure 1 identifies the heaters and coolers required for the HEN, which indicate the presence of a hot stream (FLUECOOL) or a cold stream (LNGSUPHT, WATPRHT, WATEVAP, AIRPRHT, REFPRHT, FUELPRHT), respectively. Cold streams must be heated up, while hot streams must be cooled down. Three objective functions were chosen for optimizing the operation of the system:

- Maximizing the net electrical efficiency (EFFMAX).
- Minimizing the external air flow (VAIRTOT).
- Minimizing the external water intake for reforming (VWREF).

The net electrical efficiency was calculated as explained in Section 2.1.

The selection of decision variables for the optimization involved identifying key design and operational parameters that can be manipulated to improve system performance. Five decision variables were selected along with established upper and lower limits: (i) anode off-gas recirculation ratio AOG [0, 0.60]; (ii) cathode recirculation ratio COG [0, 0.60]; (iii) external reforming ratio ER [0.20, 0.30]; (iv) stack outlet temperature TOUT [780 °C, 800 °C]; and (v) global fuel utilization GFU [0.60, 0.90]. The ER and GFU were calculated as explained in Section 2.1.

The aim of the optimization problem was to determine the values of the decision variables that maximized or minimized the objective functions. This constituted a MOO given the challenge of finding a solution fulfilling conflicting objective functions simultaneously. Addressing this challenge typically requires the use of advanced optimization algorithms (Sharma et al., 2017). In this study, the MOO problem was solved using the program Dakota, version 6.15 (Adams, B.M. et al., 2021), which provides a flexible interface between simulation codes and iterative systems analysis methods. Specifically, the multi-objective genetic algorithm (MOGA) method was used with the following parameters: population size = 40, maximum number of iterations = 3000, crossover probability = 0.95, and mutation probability = 0.1. It is important to note that the following criteria was applied to check the feasibility of the obtained solutions in the Aspen Plus model: (i) Outlet gas composition: the reducing gas content at the anode outlet must be higher than 0.1, and the oxygen content at the cathode outlet must be higher than 0.157; and (ii) cell voltage does not exceed Nernst voltage.

The result of the MOO was a set of trade-off optimal solutions, also known as non-dominated or Pareto optimal solutions. In MOO a solution is considered non-dominated when no improvement can be achieved in one objective function without a simultaneous detriment to at least one other objective (Fazlollahi et al., 2012). The set of trade-off solutions was obtained using a tool for non-dominated sorting and crowding distance calculations (Sharma et al., 2017). Table 1 presents the individual optimal solutions and compares the net electrical efficiency in the last column with respect to the highest value obtained of 51.2%.

Table 1: Individual optimal solutions (Max/Min) and chosen trade-off solution under EoL conditions.

Solution	AOG [-]	GFU [-]	ER [-]	TO [°C]	COG [-]	EFFMAX [-]	VAIRTOT [m ³ /s]	VWREF [m ³ /s]	ΔEFFMAX
Max-Eff	0.333	0.896	0.206	799.8	0.028	0.512	0.507	4.31E-06	0.0%
Min-VWREF	0.550	0.866	0.201	797.7	0.589	0.452	0.213	7.17E-07	-11.8%
Min-VAIRTOT	0.590	0.896	0.203	799.8	0.589	0.457	0.221	0.00E+00	-10.7%
Trade-off solution	0.553	0.924	0.200	800.0	0.181	0.502	0.441	0.00E+00	-1.9%

Choosing from the pool of trade-off solutions is a complex task due to compromises between conflicting objective functions and practical considerations. The fundamental question was thus whether the efficiency gain justified the higher intake of external water and air. The approach described below was adopted to determine the optimal trade-off solution for the HEN design of Section 3. The details of the selected trade-off solution are shown in Table 1. The solution is plotted along with the individual optimal solutions in the Pareto front of Figure 2.

- First, the conflicting objective functions were addressed. The use of external water for reforming emerged as a critical consideration in this study, given the technical challenges associated with implementing on-board supply of deionized water. These challenges primarily revolved around sourcing the water, allocating additional storage space, and potentially incurring higher costs. Consequently, only solutions that did not require external water intake were considered.
- Then, the trade-off solutions were analyzed by plotting the values of the decision variables against the net electrical efficiency (see Figure 2). This analysis provides insights into how the decision variables impact the objective functions. Specifically, in the context of maximizing the net electrical efficiency, it was observed that both global fuel utilization and stack outlet temperature approached their upper limits of 0.9 and 800 °C, respectively. Meanwhile, the cathode recirculation rate and the external reforming ratio converged towards their corresponding lower limits of 0 and 0.20, respectively. By contrast, the anode recirculation rate exhibited larger variations, ranging from 0.30 and 0.55. Thus, it was decided to adopt the following values for $TO_{OUT} = 800$ °C and $ER = 0.20$.
- In the specific case of the GFU, its upper limit was updated following a discussion with the stack manufacturer. Given that the actual constraint lies in the local or single-pass fuel utilization, which then determines the GFU. It was assumed that the stack outlet must have at least 10% of reducing gases (H_2+CO) to prevent oxidation of the anode. Since higher GFU generally leads to lower fuel concentration at the anode outlet, the value $GFU = 0.924$ was estimated as being the one for which the H_2+CO concentration in the AOG reaches 10%. The AOG value was adjusted accordingly to 0.553.
- In the specific case of the COG, different values were adopted for beginning- and end of life conditions as a compromise between electrical efficiency and external air flow. High COG generally leads to lower net electrical efficiency, because the high-temperature blowers in the circulation loop have a low efficiency, but it also decreases the external air flow. For EoL conditions, a value of 0.181 was selected, aligning with previous findings reported by Van Veldhuizen et al. (2023). This value reduces the external air flow for which the system must be designed. Conversely, the COG was reduced to zero for BoL conditions to ensure that the net electric efficiency reached the established target of 60%.

The results presented thus far correspond to system operation under EoL conditions. To estimate system operation under BoL conditions, the values of the decision variables were assumed to be the same as for the optimized EoL system, except for the COG as previously explained. Additionally, it was assumed that the BoL system would operate at a lower current density, providing approximately the same net power as the optimized EoL system.

Figure 2: Individual optimal solutions (Max/Min) and selected trade-off solution under EoL conditions.

The system operation of the trade-off solution at both BoL and EoL and the estimated waste heat available above 100 °C for end-of-pipe utilization are given in Table 2. The required heat loads for hot and cold streams at EoL and BoL are given in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively.

Table 2: System operation of the selected trade-off solution.

Condition	Stack power, [W]	Net power, [W]	Waste heat > 100 °C, [W]	Net electric efficiency	Gross electric efficiency	CHP efficiency
BoL	116,899	110,008	31,391	0.603	0.641	0.775
EoL	124,956	110,009	54,299	0.502	0.570	0.750

Table 3: Hot and cold streams of the selected trade-off solution under EoL conditions.

Stream	Fluid	T_{in} [°C]	T_{out} [°C]	m [kg/s]	Q [W]
<i>Hot streams</i>					
FLUECOOL-HT	Flue gas	830	100	0.524	425,729.1
FLUECOOL-LT	Flue gas	100	32	0.524	36,735.4
<i>Cold streams</i>					
LNGSUPHT	LNG	0	0	0.004	-
AIRPRHT	Air	41	678	0.520	354,423.6
REFPRHT	Fuel	605	660	0.030	3394.2
FUELPRHT	Fuel	481	700	0.030	13,612.6

3 HEN DESIGN WITH PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In the second step, the HEN was synthesized for the selected trade-off solution under EoL conditions. The data on the physical state of the SOFC system obtained in Section 2.2 was used herein. A mathematical model based on MILP was used to solve the HEN synthesis. The model was written in AMPL language (Mian et al., 2016) and solved by CPLEX solver. The problem was optimized for the minimum number of HEs, ensuring optimal matching between hot and cold streams (Yee and Grossmann, 1990). Moreover, the model considered essential practical factors which were incorporated into the MILP in the form of constraints, such as:

Table 4: Hot and cold streams of the selected trade-off solution under BoL conditions.

Stream	Fluid	T_{in} [°C]	T_{out} [°C]	m [kg/s]	Q [W]
<i>Hot streams</i>					
FLUECOOL-HT	Flue gas	830	100	0.414	337,122.0
FLUECOOL-LT	Flue gas	100	32	0.414	28,693.3
<i>Cold streams</i>					
LNGSUPHT	LNG	0	0	0.003	-
AIRPRHT	Air	38	700	0.411	291,185.4
REFPRHT	Fuel	603	665	0.025	3200.7
FUELPRHT	Fuel	481	700	0.025	11,345.3

- Adhering to safety constraints by prohibiting certain stream matches.
- Accounting for pressure drops across heat exchangers.
- Implementing a hot box to reduce heat losses.
- Preventing splitting or merging of high-temperature flows.

Furthermore, it was crucial that the HEN remained consistent for both BoL and EoL conditions of the SOFC system. Subsequently, the sizing of the HEs was determined using the logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD) method. Based on the temperature and heat load data of the flue gas exiting the HEN, the potential production of saturated steam at 180 °C and hot water at 90 °C to meet the ship's thermal requirements were estimated.

Figure 3 illustrates the grid diagram for the HEN of the selected trade-off solution. The diagram showcases the optimal matching of hot and cold streams, along with their initial and target temperatures, and the heat load of each HE. The flue gas leaving the afterburner FLUECOOL was used to meet the heat loads of the cold streams. Note that the hot stream was divided into high- and low-temperature sections at 100 °C. The cooling water (CW) provided an initial estimation of the cold utility required from 15 °C to 17 °C. The HEs exchanging heat with the CW will subsequently be replaced by end-of-pipe utilization, such as steam and hot water production.

In contrast to the simplified process flow diagram depicted in Figure 1, several distinct features characterize the HEN: (i) no external water intake is required, and (ii) there is no need for superheating LNG. Consequently, HEs 4, 5 and 6, connected to cold streams LNGSUPHT, WATEVAP and WATPRHT are not required for the steady-state operation of the system. However, they were included in the network (represented by dotted lines) to facilitate system start-up.

The optimal solution consisted of 9 HEs: HEs 1 through 6 are placed inside the hot box of the SOFC, while HEs 7 through 9 use cold utility CW. As previously explained, HEs 7, 8 and 9 represent the potential for end-of-pipe utilization, while HEs 4, 5 and 6 account for system start-up considerations. The flue gas FLUECOOL-HT leaving the afterburner was split to meet the heat demand of each cold stream. The hot streams leaving HEs 2 and 3 offer the potential for high-temperature heat recovery at about 604.9 °C and 738.8 °C, respectively. After delivering their heat loads to the corresponding cold streams, the several splits were merged at 100 °C constituting the low-temperature flue gas FLUECOOL-LT.

The heat recovery was assumed to take place in counterflow HEs with constant specific heat capacities. Given the heat load in the HE, the heat transfer surface area A [m²] can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$A = \frac{Q}{U \cdot LMTD} \quad (2)$$

where, Q [W] is the heat load of the HE provided by the MILP model, U [W/m²/K] is the overall heat transfer coefficient, Eq. (2), and $LMTD$ [K] is the logarithmic mean temperature difference, see Eq. (3).

Figure 3: Initial grid diagram for the HEN under EoL conditions.

The overall heat transfer coefficient U depends on the individual heat transfer coefficients k of the hot h and cold c streams in the HE, which vary according to the phase of the flow, and can be calculated from Eq. (2): (i) gas stream: $60 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$; (ii) liquid stream: $560 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$; and (iii) phase-change stream: $3600 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$.

$$\frac{1}{U} = \frac{1}{k_h} + \frac{1}{k_c} \quad (3)$$

The $LMTD$ in the HE was obtained by the following equation:

$$LMTD = \frac{(T_{h,in} - T_{c,out}) - (T_{h,out} - T_{c,in})}{\ln((T_{h,in} - T_{c,out}) / (T_{h,out} - T_{c,in}))} \quad (4)$$

where subindices h and c represent hot and cold streams, respectively, entering and leaving the HE. The results of the HEN synthesis of the trade-off solution are given in Table 5. The estimated HE area was 124.54 m^2 . Note that the area excludes the HEs connected to CW, as they would be replaced for the end-of-pipe utilization. For a preliminary volume estimation, it was assumed that 1 m^2 would correspond to 0.005 m^3 . Thus, the estimated volume was 0.623 m^3 . It was observed that HE1 (FLUECOOL-AIRPRHT) was the largest in area and heat load.

The procedure was repeated considering the system operating conditions at BoL. The results are shown in Table 6. While the thermal requirements of the BoL system are lower than in EoL conditions, the generated waste heat was enough to cover the system's thermal requirements. The HEN layout remained consistent: the same HEs were installed with the same hot and cold streams matches.

For practical considerations regarding the hot box of the SOFC system, two alternative configurations were proposed to reduce the number of outlets from the hot box with respect to the initial configuration displayed in Figure 3. As explained in the following paragraphs, this was achieved by merging certain hot flows. There were two main challenges associated with these configurations: Firstly, merging streams at different temperatures inevitably results in an exergy loss, which has an impact on the amount of steam that can be produced. This point will be discussed in Section 4. Secondly, the use of high-temperature valves for merging the hot streams may present challenges related to reliability and cost. Figure 5 presents the alternative configuration with two outlets, where the hot streams leaving HEs 2 and 3 are merged. Merging the two hot streams at different temperatures ($604.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $738.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) resulted in a single flow at $655.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Likewise, Figure 6 presents the alternative configuration with only one outlet, where the hot streams leaving HEs 1, 2 and 3 are merged, resulting in a single flow at $193 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 5: HEN synthesis under EoL conditions.

Hot-cold streams	HE	Q [W]	$T_{h,in}$ [K]	$T_{h,out}$ [K]	$T_{c,in}$ [K]	$T_{c,out}$ [K]	U [W/m ² /K]	$LMTD$ [K]	A [m ²]
FLUECOOL-AIRPRHT	1	354423.0	1103.15	373.15	314.15	951.15	30	98.27	120.22
FLUECOOL-FUELPRHT	2	13612.0	1103.15	878.04	754.15	973.15	30	126.92	3.57
FLUECOOL-REFPRHT	3	3394.0	1103.15	1011.93	878.15	933.15	30	151.17	0.75
FLUECOOL-CW	7	30530	878.04	373.15	288.15	290.15	54	260.04	2.17
FLUECOOL-CW	8	23768	1011.93	373.15	288.15	290.15	54	297.69	1.47
FLUECOOL-CW	9	36735	373.15	305.15	288.15	290.15	54	41.62	16.29

Table 6: HEN synthesis under BoL conditions.

Hot-cold streams	HE	Q [W]	$T_{h,in}$ [K]	$T_{h,out}$ [K]	$T_{c,in}$ [K]	$T_{c,out}$ [K]	U [W/m ² /K]	$LMTD$ [K]	A [m ²]
FLUECOOL-AIRPRHT	1	291185.0	1103.15	373.15	311.15	973.15	30	91.84	105.68
FLUECOOL-FUELPRHT	2	11345.0	1103.15	838.14	754.15	973.15	30	105.33	3.59
FLUECOOL-REFPRHT	3	3200.0	1103.15	944.04	876.15	938.15	30	109.35	0.98
FLUECOOL-CW	7	19906	878.04	373.15	288.15	290.15	54	260.04	1.41
FLUECOOL-CW	8	11483	1011.93	373.15	288.15	290.15	54	297.69	0.71
FLUECOOL-CW	9	28693	373.15	305.15	288.15	290.15	54	41.62	12.72

4 END-OF-PIPE UTILIZATION

The third step of the HEN design optimization consisted in evaluating the maximum waste heat recovery for producing saturated steam at 180 °C and hot water at 90 °C. The following assumptions were made:

- The flue gas can be cooled down up to 100 °C.
- Specific heat of the flue gas $c_p = 1.112$ kJ/(kg·K).
- Temperature differences in the heat recovery steam generator (HRSG): Approach temperature $\Delta T_{\text{approach}} = 37$ °C and Pinch point $\Delta T_{\text{pinch}} = 15$ °C.

Figure 6 displays the temperature profile of the flue gas and saturated steam production circuit at 180 °C starting from hot water at 90 °C. For the hot side, the inlet temperature $T_{h,in}$ of the flue gas entering HE 7 (and HE 8, depending on the case) and the corresponding heat load Q were taken. From the cold side, the specific enthalpies h of water were taken for liquid water at 90 °C and 143 °C, and saturated steam at 180 °C. The maximum production of hot water at 90 °C, starting from water at 25 °C, was estimated by considering the available heat load from the temperature range of the flue gas exiting the HRSG, from $T_{h,out}$ to 100 °C.

Table 7 presents the estimated steam and hot water production under BoL and EoL conditions for the three HEN configurations presented in the previous section. The information in the table is complemented by the information showcased in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5. As can be observed, the amount of steam and hot water obtainable by the initial HEN (Figure 3) and the configuration with two hot outlet streams (Figure 4) was virtually the same. By contrast, the configuration with only one hot outlet stream (Figure 5) proved to be unfeasible from the perspective of steam production, as the resulting temperature of the flue gas is below the required temperature for steam production (see the HRSG in Figure 6).

Figure 4: Alternative grid diagram for the HEN under EoL conditions with two outlet hot streams.

Figure 5: Alternative grid diagram for the HEN under EoL conditions with one outlet hot stream.

Figure 6: Temperature profile in the heat recovery steam generator.

Table 7: Estimated steam and hot water production under EoL and BoL conditions.

Configuration	FLUECOOL split	BoL			EoL		
		<i>T</i> [°C]	Steam [kg/day]	Hot water [kg/day]	<i>T</i> [°C]	Steam [kg/day]	Hot water [kg/day]
Initial (Figure 3)	a	100.0	0.0	0.0	100	0.0	0.0
	b	565.0	629.2	770.8	604.9	984.6	1009.5
	c	670.9	380.2	292.2	738.9	803.7	457.6
2 outlet hot streams (Figure 4)	a	100.0	0.0	0.0	100	0.0	0.0
	b + c	598.8	1009.3	1062.9	655.9	1788.3	1467.1
1 outlet hot stream (Figure 5)	a + b + c	168.0	0.0	14334.0	193.1	0.0	17621.2

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study performed the HEN design of a 125 kW SOFC cogeneration system with particular focus on its practical implementation. The HEN was designed for EoL conditions of the SOFC system, and a verification was made to ensure that the network remained consistent for BoL system operation. The takeaways from the development of the study are: (i) hot box considerations: consider forbidden matches between hot and cold streams, reducing the number of streams entering or leaving the hot box to minimize heat losses; (ii) sequential vs. parallel layout: account for pressure drops in sequential HEs with large area differences, and avoid flow splitting/merging at high temperature; (iii) EoL and BoL conditions: varying temperatures and mass flowrates impact on the HEN design and their corresponding area and volume; and (iv) deionized water usage: additional on-board tank volume becomes an issue. Future work will perform the optimization of the HEN with different objectives, such as area or investment cost. The HEN can also be improved by considering system start-up conditions. Moreover, a two-stage approach can be developed to tackle the simultaneous optimization of the SOFC system and HEN, but it would involve addressing challenges related to non-linear behaviour of the heat transfer taking place in the HEs and the heat requirements of the system's streams.

NOMENCLATURE

A	heat transfer surface area	(m ²)
h	specific enthalpy	(kJ/kg)
k	heat transfer coefficient	(W/m ² /K)
LHV _{LNG}	lower heating value of LNG	(kJ/mol)
LMTD	logarithmic mean temperature difference	(K)
m	mass flowrate	(kg/s)
\dot{m}_{LNG}	molar flow rate of LNG	(mol/s)
P _{aux}	auxiliary power consumed by blowers and pumps	(W)
P _{SOFC}	gross power output	(W)
Q	heat load	(W)
T	temperature	(°C) or (K)
TOUT	stack outlet temperature	(°C)
U	overall heat transfer coefficient	(W/m ² /K)
VAIRTOT	external air flow	(m ³ /s)
VWREF	external water intake for reforming	(m ³ /s)
η_{el}	net electrical efficiency	(%)

Subscript

c,	cold stream
h	hot stream
in	inlet
out	outlet

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